

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6374216>

RESEARCH OF SOCIAL CONFLICTS AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: *This article discusses the main problems that are studied by conflictology. The social conflict and their diagnostic study are analyzed*

Keywords: *analysis of social conflict, diagnostics, components, stages, research*

The consequences of the global financial and economic crisis in our country are accompanied by an increase in social tension and conflict in society, manifested primarily in the growth of individual and collective intolerant, conflict and protest behavior.

Throughout its history, humanity has accumulated considerable experience in nonviolent resolution of social conflicts. However, only since the second half of the XX century, when it became obvious that conflicts are a real threat to humanity, an independent field of knowledge began to take shape in the world – conflictology. The practical purpose of conflictology is the analysis and diagnosis of social conflicts with a view to their subsequent resolution.

The term "diagnostics" in Greek means "recognition". This special method of studying various phenomena and processes was first widely used in medicine and psychology. Based on the principle of analogies, diagnostics consists in recognizing the general, abstract in the particular, concrete.

The problems related to the content of the process of diagnosing conflicts as the basis for their resolution are mainly theoretical and methodological in nature. The famous American sociologist and conflictologist Lewis Kouser in the 1950s was one of the first to discuss issues related to the diagnosis of social conflict. Among them it should be noted:

- identification of determinants of social conflict;
- determination of the parameters of the severity and duration of social conflict;
- identification of the grounds for classifying conflicts.

L. Kouser's position contributed to the understanding of social conflict as one of the forms of social interaction, which under certain conditions causes not only destructive, but also constructive consequences for the social system and its subsystems. This new approach to the diagnosis and practical settlement and resolution of social conflicts provided, in fact,

not only their theoretical modeling and expertise, but also prepared the ground for the transfer of the latter to the technological level.

The problem of diagnosing social conflict in Russian science is not widely presented. Referring to the schemes of conflict analysis reflected in the literature, one can find a certain similarity in the views of specialists about them.

Thus, A.Y. Antsupov and A.I. Shipilov, authors of an interdisciplinary review on conflictology, come to the conclusion that conflict analysis can be based on the following groups of basic categories: the essence of conflict, its genesis, classification, dynamics, functions. L.A. Petrovskaya, who proposed the first conceptual scheme of socio-psychological conflict analysis includes four main categorical groups: the structure of the conflict, its dynamics, functions and typology. We will confine ourselves to these examples, since referring to the works of other authors does not actually introduce anything fundamentally new into understanding the content of the structural and dynamic characteristics of the conflict, as which the subjects of the conflict, the subject of the conflict and its dynamics are almost always distinguished.

In the process of solving problems concerning the choice of the main categories of description of the phenomenon, the question of the grounds for distinguishing certain concepts as necessary and sufficient becomes fundamental. However, the point is not to designate the largest number of categories describing the conflict or to achieve maximum differentiation of its elements. The content of conflict diagnostics in the context of its subsequent resolution is the process of studying this social phenomenon, identifying cause-and-effect relationships characterizing its condition, and the results of influencing it in order to eliminate negative trends.

Social conflict can be defined as a process of counteraction of social actors aimed at resolving contradictions in their interests and goals. The initial methodological position in the analysis of social conflicts can be the idea that conflict is a constantly present type of social relationships in society.

There are three mandatory components of any social conflict

- 1) the presence of two or more sides;
- 2) conduct of counteraction by the parties;
- 3) the possibility of assessing the opposition of the parties by an external observer.

Proponents of the theory of conflict explain the whole social life as naturally conflictual.

Conflict is seen as a normal and even necessary social phenomenon. This position is most clearly reflected in the works of famous scientists G. Simmel, R. Darendorff, L. Kouser, L. Krisberg.

Domestic conflict theorists include A. Zdravomyslov, F. Borodkin, A. Zaitsev, V. Kudryavtsev, E. Stepanov, Yu. Rastov, V. Shalenko, etc.

In the process of conflict diagnosis, first of all it is necessary

1. Make sure that we are dealing with a conflict, and not with a phenomenon that looks like it.

2. To begin the diagnosis of the conflict with the analysis of the full composition of its participants, and not with finding out the causes of the conflict.

3. Follow a certain sequence of diagnostic research operations.

4. Adhere to the equal treatment of the parties to the conflict in the diagnostic process.

5. Not to give recommendations on conflict resolution until the entire process of its diagnosis is completed.

In the process of conflict diagnosis, we recommend the following sequence of research operations:

1. Determination of the full composition of participants (subjects) of the conflict and their roles in the conflict.

2. Identification of the subject of the conflict.

3. Finding out all the resources of the parties to the conflict and the balance of their forces.

4. Definition of the type of this conflict.

5. Identification of the sources of the conflict – its cause, pretext, views of the parties about the situation, the totality of causes and the root cause.

6. Clarification of the interests of each of the conflicting parties.

7. Consideration of the goals of the conflicting parties, the degree of their opposition and the measure of compliance with the interests of the parties to the conflict.

8. Finding out the price and the sign of the conflict. Drawing up a conflict formula.

9. Choosing the optimal way to resolve the conflict.

Thus, the diagnosis of a social conflict is a detailed analysis of a single conflict, involving finding answers to a whole series of questions about the main characteristics of the conflict under study and, above all, about its causes. The diagnosis of the conflict ends with the determination of the optimal way to solve it.

The way to resolve a conflict is a combination of certain methods of its completion: violent or peaceful. This is not a randomly chosen method of conflict resolution, but directly dependent on the indications of its previous diagnosis. The models used in conflict resolution are formed on the basis of the cultural and legal attitudes existing in society in relation to the conflict, encouraging or prohibiting one or another way of its resolution.

Historically , there have been five main approaches to resolving social conflicts in Russian society:

- 1) from a position of strength;
- 2) from the position of law;
- 3) from the position of nonviolence and compromise;
- 4) from the perspective of integrating the interests of the parties to the conflict;
- 5) from the position of isolation of the parties to the conflict.

Conclusion. The formation of institutions of peaceful conflict resolution in modern Uzbekistan is still at an initial stage. For this reason, many questions are presented by us so far only in a staged plan. This is due to their insufficient development in modern domestic and foreign sociological and conflictological literature.

REFERENCES:

1. Darendorf, R. Elementy teorii socialnogo konflikta / Sociologicheskie issledovaniya. – 1994. – №5.
2. Krisberg, L. Miro - sozidanie, miro - soxranenie i razreshenie konfliktov/ Sociologicheskie issledovaniya. - 1990. - No.11.
3. Petrovskaya, L.A. O ponyatiynoy sxeme socialno - psixologicheskogo analiza konflikta / Teoreticheskie i metodologicheskie problemy socialnoy psixologii. - M., 1977.